
USE OF E-RESOURCES OF NATIONAL POWER TRAINING INSTITUTE: A CASE STUDY

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Abstract:

In this paper issues like use of electronic information sources, CBT packages, their impact on print sources, and awareness of these sources among users as well as the places where these resources are used. National Power Training Institute has good academic policies given in the Nation policy of education 2022. The paper traces the problems and prospectus of educational resources available on the website of National Power Training Institute, in views on the ideal and current situation of education in Power Plant Engineering in academies.

Keywords: *E-Resources, Problems, Prospectus, Education, Resources, Centers, National Power Training Institute*

Introduction:

The progress and sudden changes in information dissemination with the help of information communication technology brought drastic changes in libraries and knowledge and information centers. Various forms of information resources have been easily handled and accessed that fulfilled demand of the users and provide satisfaction to them. Information technology has become an important tool for retrieving the information-resources has been increased it's necessary study on the different aspects of e-resources to the use of e-resources of training institutions. This study is an attempt to analyze the use of e-resources at the National Power Training Institute's-resources provides improving access to information as compare to traditional methods of information dissemination. National Power Training Institute Libraries collect, organizes and disseminates materials

useful for persons working in power plants. Material may be varied, including training manuals; Computer based training, reports as well as directories, books, posters, leaflets, videos, games and sample of equipment. Libraries of National Power Training Institute actively seeks to disseminate, share the information, material they have. National Power Training Institute Library staff always motivates, encourages, and cooperates to use the material. They always help users to find out material of their choice and need. They produce locally adopted materials, information packs for dissemination. National Power Training Institute organizes training, discussion workshops, exhibitions, post graduate training programs for companies. National Power Training Institute provides pleasant environment for studying in campus area National Power Training Institute Libraries contain relevant and accessible

resource collection regarding power based on users need.

The History of National Power Training Institute:

National Power Training Institute is a Government training institution under the Ministry of Power, Government of India with its Cooperate Office at Faridabad. For more than five decades National Power Training Institute has been providing dedicated service. The Central water and Power Commission (Power Wing) established Thermal Power Station Personnel; Training Institutes in 1965-1975 t Neyveli (1965), Durgapur (1968), Badarpur, Delhi (1974) and Nagpur (1975) for training the engineers of thermal Power Stations which were being established in the country during the time. National Power Training Institute established “Power System Training Institute (PSTI) in 1972 and Hot Line Training Center (HLTC) in 1974 at Bengaluru. With the bifurcation of the Central water and Power Commission into the Central Electricity Authority (CEA) and Central Water Commission (CWC) in the 1970s, the Institute came under the Central Electrical Authority (CEA). In the Late 1970s, the Raj Dekshya Committee set up by the Government of India to improve Power sector of the country recommended among many things formal training for the personnel employed in the Power industry”. To make Training mandatory for generating stations and associated substations personnel, Indian Electricity Rule was amended. With this the Thermal Power Station Personnel Training Institutes under the Central Electricity Authority were carved out and formed into a separate autonomous body under the Ministry of Power as the Power Engineers Training Society (PETS) in

1980 to give more importance to Power Training and to have an accelerated growth of the Institutes. Later, in 1993 Power Engineers Training Institute was renamed as National Power Training Institute (NPTI). Power Systems Training Institute (PSTI) and Hot Line Training Centre (HLTC) were merged with NPTI in 2002. The National Power Training Institute (NPTI) grew continuously through the tenure of Indian Governments. National Power Training Institute previously conducted training only in Thermal Power Generation. This is now get equipped itself to conduct training in all segments of power sector like generation, transmission and distribution. National Power Training Institute trained thousands of Engineers, Supervisors and Technicians from most of the Electricity Boards, Public and Personnel from developing nations in the last four decades of its existence.

Ideology for Methodizing Educational Resource Centers:

Organized Educational Resource Centers must have the following Units:

- The Information Unit
- The Reference Unit
- Curriculum Development Unit
- The Production Unit
- Education Research Unit
- Science Development Unit’
- Language Development Unit
- Guidance and Counseling unit
- Audio Visual Unit
- Examination/Certification Unit
- Library Unit
- Curriculum and External Services Unit
- Storage Unit
- Computer Unit

Current General Situation of E-Resource in National Power Training Institute:

A Multimedia Computer Based Training (CBT) Center has been established at National Power Training Institute's Corporate Office and it's Regional Institutes for developing Multimedia CBTs in various Technical areas concerning Power Generation like Thermal, CCGT /Gas, Hydro, Renewable Transmission & distribution and Management areas. In the website of the National Power Training Institute under e-resources heading E-resources are accessible openly.

Publications: 99 Training manuals are published and available for trainees.

Reports: 73 numbers of reports in downloadable form are of various governments agencies are available.

Policies: 21 numbers of Government Policies in the Power Sector are available on the website.

Presentations: 227 Presentations of the latest trends in the Power Sector are provided as Open-source resource.

Downloads: Total 54 pdf files are made available for users in downloadable form under this head.

Sr. No.	Name of the Multimedia CBT Package
1.	Coal Thermal
2.	Boilers
3.	Combustion system in Boilers
4.	Boiler drum and Drum Internals
5.	Super Heater, Re-heater and De-Super heater
6.	Air Heater
7.	Fuel Handling System, Feed Heating and Exhaust system
8.	CFB Boiler
9.	Turbines
10.	Water/Steam cycle of a Thermal Power Plant
11.	Steam Turbine Constructiob
12.	Turbine Governing System (KWU)
13.	Regenerative Feed Heating System
14.	Turbine vaccum System

More than 99 Publications are available in the institute level of the National Power Training Institutes of India. Some of them are cited below:

1	Thermal Power Plant Familiarization Vol 1
2	Thermal Power Plant Familiarization Vol 2
3	Thermal Power Plant Familiarization Vol 3
4	Thermal Power Plant familiarization Vol 4
5	Thermal Power Plant Operation
6	Thermal Power Plant Metallurgy
7	Control And Instrumentation Vol 1
8	Control And Instrumentation Vol 2
9	Control And Instrumentation Vol 3
10	Fans and Air Heaters
11	Fans and Air Heaters (Hindi)
12	Compressor And Compressed Air

13	Motor Maintenance
14	Battery Maintenance
15	Battery Maintenance(Hindi)

More than 72 E-Reports are accessible on the Website of the National Power Training Institutes of India .Some of them are cited below:

1	CEA-Office order for constitution of 11 No of Sub Committees under Committee for National Electricity Plan,2015
2	CEA-NEP-Minutes of the meeting of Committee for National electricity Plan ,2015
3	CEA-NEP-Office order for constitution of Comittee for National Electricity Plan,2015
4	National Electricity policy
5	Global Coal Production Data
6	CEA Report on Fly ash Utilization, Jan 2014
7	Growth of Electricity Sector In India From 1974-2013 by CEA
8	Failure of 220 KV and above voltage class substation equipment
9	Cost comparison of various fuel options.
10	CEA Report on Grid Integration of Renewable Energy source.
11	First Annual Integrated ratings of State Distribution Utilities Approved by Ministry of Power.
12	Growth of Electricity Sector in India from 1947-2013 by CEA

More than 50 E-Policies are accessible on the website of the National Power Training Institutes of India. Some of them are as follows

Sr. No.	Title	Policy Year
1	National Training Policy	2017
2	Power Compendium	2011
3	Policies on Renewable	2008
4	Transmission Projects and Tariff based bidding Guidelines	2005
5	Electricity Act with Amendment	2003
6	ECIs Course book on Regulatory for A&B Categories	
7	Call Center Metrics	
8	Data Center Maintenance	
9	Regulation and Commercial issues in Bulk Generation Tariff	
10	ESIC Course Book on Regulatory for A&B Categories	
11	Call Centre Matrics	
12	Data Center Physical Security	

More than 300 E-Presentations are accessible on the website of the National Power Training Institutes of India.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

Based on the website of the National Power Training Institute it is observed that training Institute Libraries in developing countries continues to subscribe information resources through Consortium Building. All the resources are according to cater needs of users. Appropriate funds must be provided for subscriptions of such valuable resources in digital form. Also old documents and reports of different Power Stations are to be shared digitally for more usage and rare

information resources will be made available for all.

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